

Mother's Milk is Boon for Infants

Paper Id : 20404 Submission Date : 2025-06-07 Acceptance Date : 2025-06-21 Publication Date : 2025-06-25

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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.16872566

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Abstract

Milk secreted from female mammary glands after giving birth to baby is called mother's milk or breast milk. It is beneficial for both mother and infants. It contains all essential nutrients that are fruitful for growth and development throughout lifespan of living beings. Breast milk provides all the nutritional needs of infants. It provides protection against different types of disease. Thus build strong immune system. Infants are the future of any Nation, so baby should not be discarded from his/her right to obtain mother's milk. But the problems are that majority of infants are not getting mother's milk due to some reasons. The reasons must be sort out through scientific research, nutritionist and social research worker. Policies should be made regarding this to solve problem forever. One of the best idea to provide nutrition education concerning how to improve secretion of milk. Breastfed infants will become healthy, wealthy and wise in future and Nation will prosper in all the fields. Hence, mother's milk is considered as a boon for infants and Nation.

Keywords Mother's milk, Nutrients, Immunity, Growth, Development.

Introduction

The first discharge of mother's milk is called colostrum. It is also known as yellow gold. Because it has much benefits in providing immunity that carries all future functions of body till old age. For infants mother's milk is precious nutritious food. Till six months infants should be provided with only mother's milk and nothing else. If mothers milk is not available than only other options should be used such as formula milk. Therefore, it is necessary for health worker to go in community and society and give nutrition education regarding breast feed to women of child bearing age. The health condition of infants will be better and it will continue till old age. There will be absence of disease and health complications to much extent.

Objective of study

1. To highlight the nutritional, immunological, and developmental importance of mother's milk for infants and its long-term benefits for both child and mother.
2. To investigate the underlying causes preventing infants from receiving adequate breast milk, including physiological, social, cultural, and economic factors.
3. To assess the awareness and practices of breastfeeding among mothers, caregivers, and communities.
4. To examine the role of nutrition education and public health initiatives in promoting optimal lactation and breastfeeding practices.
5. To propose effective strategies and policy recommendations aimed at increasing breastfeeding rates and addressing barriers to successful breastfeeding.

6. To advocate for the recognition of breastfeeding as a fundamental right of every infant, essential for national health and development.

Review of Literature

Infants will acquire normal health that is height and weight of infants in the long run will be according to age and produce pleasing personality. It has been seen in many studies that stunting in infants is due to bottle feeding (Yirgu Fekadu et al. 02 Sep 2015). Exclusive breastfeeding reduces the leading cause of death due to diarrhoea and pneumonia (Black et al. 2008). Breast feeding promotes epithelial recovery from infection and intestinal maturation (Neovita, 2016). The Lancet. April 2016). It has been seen in a study that only 3 percent mothers were aware about colostrum that it is nutritious (Kulsum et al. 2008).

Main Text

Mother's milk is boon for infants due to following reasons:

1. **Mother's milk provides perfect nutrition to infants:** During the first day after the birth of the baby mammary gland discharge yellow fluid, called colostrum which is rich in protein low in sugar and also contains useful compounds which cannot be replaceable by any other formula milk. It is really a amazing food produced by female mammary glands.
2. **Mother's milk contains useful antibodies:** Mother's milk contains antibodies that protects the infants from virus and bacteria. In early months these bacteria and viruses are critical for baby. Antibodies immunizes baby, forms layer which protects the nose of baby, throat of the baby and digestive system of the baby. Many studies showed that infants who were not breast fed are having risk of pneumonia, diarrhoea and infections like health issues.
3. **Mother's milk lowers disease risk:** It protects against cancer and many more disease in long term. Mothers who breast fed are having less chance of breast and ovarian cancer.
4. **Mother's milk saves time and money:** By breast feeding mothers do not have to spend money on formula milk. Do not have to spend time in cleaning bottle and sterilizing it.
5. **Mother's milk lowers the risk of illness:** Exclusive breast feed may reduce many illness such as middle ear infections, throat, and sinuses infections. It protects against acute respiratory infections and gastrointestinal infections. Infants who are exclusive breastfed are less likely to get serious cold, ear and throat infections. Breast feeding is useful for having less chance of gut infections in infants. Also asthma and allergies are less likely make them prey. In later years of life when they grow older they have less likely to get Blood Pressure, Heart Stroke, Diabetes, Cancer.
6. **Mothers who breastfed have lower risk of depression:** Mothers who breast fed are less likely to get depression as compare to who do not breastfed after postpartum.
7. **Mother's milk considered best for infant:** The component of breast milk are lactose. Protein (casein and whey), fat, which are easily digestible by baby. Breast-milk contains essential nutrients that are best for the growth of brain of baby and also for the development of nervous system of the baby. Breast fed babies are less likely to get eye problems because it contains certain fats that protect eyes.
8. **Mother's milk contains key hormone:** Breast fed babies get key hormone called leptin in their system which regulate appetite and fat storage.
9. **Develop healthy eating pattern:** Breastfed baby self- regulate milk intake and hence develop healthy eating pattern.

Problems in Breast Feeding

Sometime mothers have health complications so it is suggested not to breastfeed. Many times it happens mothers get sore nipple so during that it is not likely to be able to breastfed. Majority of mothers complain about not secretion of breast milk. Hormonal imbalance may also be the reason of low secretion of milk. This is a serious issue and this should not be overlooked .Due to cesarean mothers are not able to breastfeed in comfortable position.

Solution of Secretion of Mother's Milk

Some low cost recipes are available which mothers can get benefited through them by applying in their diet. Such as mansoor dal, Oats in milk, Garlic cooked in meals, Fenugreek tea in their diet to increase secretion of milk so that infants get proper, adequate diet to satisfy their hunger .Balanced healthy diet containing proteins, vegetables, fruits and whole grains are perfect to increase secretion of milk.

Conclusion

Hence it is concluded that mother's milk is precious nutrition for infants and it is a boon for them. It should be maintained properly by every mother. Policies to be framed to increase the secretion of mother's milk so that they can feed their baby sufficiently. Mother's milk lowers the risk of morbidity, mortality and malnutrition to much extent. It also boosts the immune system so that communicable and non-communicable diseases cannot occur quite often.

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